

Formulation and Evaluation of a Therapeutic Nail Lacquer Enriched with *Allium sativum* and *Melaleuca alternifolia* for Effective Trans-ungual Delivery in the Treatment of Onychomycosis

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ABSTRACT

Onychomycosis, a prevalent fungal infection affecting the nails, remains challenging to treat due to limited penetration of topical agents and the adverse reactions linked with systemic antifungal drugs. The present research was aimed at formulating an antifungal nail lacquer using natural bio actives, namely garlic extract (allicin) and tea tree oil, incorporated within a polymeric film-forming base. The formulation strategy was intended to improve adhesion, ensure prolonged retention on the nail surface, and enhance therapeutic effectiveness while reducing the drawbacks associated with conventional dosage forms such as creams, ointments, gels, and oral medications. The prepared nail lacquer was subjected to evaluation for its physicochemical and functional attributes to determine the most effective composition. Overall, this approach highlights a potential patient-friendly and safe alternative for the management of nail fungal infections.

Keywords: Onychomycosis, *Allium sativum*, *Melaleuca alternifolia*, Ethyl cellulose, Antifungal nail lacquer.

Figure 1: Graphical Abstract

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INTRODUCTION

Onychomycosis is a chronic fungal infection that affects the nail unit, involving either toenails or fingernails, though it is far more common in toenails. When the infection is caused by dermatophytes, it is specifically termed *tinea unguium*. Nails that are damaged or deformed due to non-fungal causes are referred to as dystrophic nails. This condition affects over 19% of the global population and ranks among the most frequently encountered nail disorders in clinical practice. It not only causes physical discomfort but also psychological distress, significantly impacting quality of life. Several clinical types of Onychomycoses exist, among which distal subungual onychomycosis is the most common form, affecting the nail bed, plate, and hyponychium. It typically originates from a fungal infection of the surrounding skin, such as *tinea pedis*. Infected nails often become thickened, discoloured, brittle, and misshapen. While not fatal, untreated onychomycosis can lead to serious complications, including cellulitis, sepsis, osteomyelitis, permanent nail loss, and tissue damage. [1-3] However, the term "onychomycosis" broadly includes infections caused by dermatophytes, yeasts, and non-dermatophyte molds. Dermatophytes, especially *Trichophyton rubrum* and *T. mentagrophytes*, are the most common culprits. Yeasts, mainly *Candida albicans*, typically affect fingernails, especially in immunocompromised individuals. NDMs like *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, and *Scopulariopsis brevicaulis* commonly infect toenails and are more prevalent in certain regions and among immunosuppressed patients. [4] Essential oils are natural antiseptic compounds produced by plants. Tea tree oil (TTO), extracted through steam distillation from the Australian plant *Melaleuca alternifolia*, is widely used as a topical antimicrobial agent. It exhibits broad-spectrum activity against various pathogens, including bacteria, viruses, fungi, yeasts, and dermatophytes. TTO is composed of over 100 chemical constituents, predominantly terpenes—mainly monoterpenes and sesquiterpenes. Among these, terpinen-4-ol is the primary active component and is largely responsible for TTO's potent antifungal effects. It enhances antifungal activity by damaging the fungal cell membrane and disrupting efflux pump mechanisms, thereby increasing the cell's susceptibility to drugs like fluconazole. [5-7] Among

natural substances, garlic shows stronger antifungal activity compared to others like turmeric and neem. Garlic's active compound, allicin, inhibits a key enzyme vital for many microorganisms. Fresh garlic extract demonstrated stronger antifungal effects against *Candida albicans* than garlic powder, producing larger inhibition zones. Higher concentrations of garlic extract increase fungal growth inhibition. Other research also confirms the antifungal potential of plant-based extracts and compares them favorably with standard antifungal drugs. [8-11] Transungual drug delivery refers to the transport of medication through the nail plate to achieve targeted treatment of nail disorders. The term "transungual" combines "trans" (meaning "through") and "unguis" (meaning "nail"). Compared to oral or systemic drug delivery, unguinal therapy offers several advantages—it is simpler to formulate, avoids systemic side effects, and eliminates drug interactions. Topical treatment is particularly beneficial for managing onychomycosis, as it delivers the drug directly to the infection site while minimizing unwanted effects. However, challenges such as the nail's low permeability and limited blood flow in the affected area often lead to insufficient drug levels. These issues can be addressed by topical application. Traditional formulations are often ineffective for nail treatment, as they are easily removed by washing or friction. To overcome these limitations, medicated nail lacquers have been developed to enhance drug penetration through the nail plate, improving the effectiveness of antifungal therapy for onychomycosis. [12-14] Medicated nail lacquers represent an effective transungual drug delivery system, offering enhanced antifungal activity. Upon application, the volatile components of the lacquer evaporate, forming an occlusive film on the nail surface. This process results in a higher localized drug concentration compared to the initial formulation, thereby increasing the concentration gradient and promoting improved permeation through the thick keratinized structure of the nail plate.

In this scholarly research article, we have developed and evaluated a novel medicated nail lacquer formulated with tea tree oil and garlic extract for the effective treatment of onychomycosis, a common fungal infection of the nails. The selection of these natural agents was based on their well-documented

broad-spectrum antifungal properties and minimal side effects, making them promising alternatives to conventional synthetic antifungals. Tea tree oil, extracted from *Melaleuca alternifolia*, is known for its potent antifungal activity due to its high content of terpinen-4-ol, which disrupts fungal cell membranes and enhances the efficacy of conventional drugs by interfering with fungal efflux pumps. Garlic extract, rich in allicin, acts by inhibiting key microbial enzymes such as succinate dehydrogenase, thereby compromising fungal metabolism and survival. Studies have shown that both agents are effective individually, but their combined application may offer synergistic antifungal effects, improving treatment outcomes. The formulation of a nail lacquer allows for targeted transungual drug delivery, ensuring prolonged contact with the infected nail site, overcoming the natural barrier properties of the nail plate, and minimizing systemic absorption and associated side effects. Nail lacquers also offer better patient compliance due to ease of application, reduced dosing frequency, and cosmetic acceptability. The developed nail lacquer represents a safe, effective, and natural approach to managing onychomycosis, supporting the growing interest in plant-based, targeted therapies in modern dermatological treatment.

1.1 Plant profile:

➤ *Allium sativum*

Garlic has been widely used in traditional and alternative medicine due to its powerful therapeutic properties, which are primarily attributed to allicin, a sulfur-containing compound formed when garlic is crushed. Allicin has broad-spectrum antibacterial activity, specifically targeting dermatophytes such as *Trichophyton rubrum* and *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, which are significant causes of onychomycosis (fungal nail infection).

• Geographical location:

Garlic (*Allium sativum* L.), a member of the Alliaceae family, is well known for its dual role as a culinary spice and a traditional medicinal agent. Thought to have originated in Central Asia, garlic gradually spread across China, the Near East, the Mediterranean region, and eventually to Europe, North Africa, and

Mexico. Historical records suggest its medicinal use dates back over 5,000 years, with early references found in Sanskrit texts. Garlic held significant importance in ancient Egyptian, Babylonian, Greek, and Roman civilizations for its healing properties. Its antibacterial potential was scientifically recognized in the 19th century when Louis Pasteur documented its ability to combat bacterial infections.

• Chemical Constituents:

Garlic includes around 33 sulfur compounds, 17 amino acids, many enzymes, and minerals like selenium. It has the largest concentration of sulfur compounds, i.e., allicin, allin, and diallyl sulphide, among *Allium* species. The primary sulfur compound in garlic is alliin, which transforms into the physiologically active molecule allicin when garlic is crushed or sliced. Allicin is responsible for many of garlic's medical actions, notably its antibacterial capabilities. The transformation of alliin into allicin occurs rapidly after injury to the bulb. Other forms of garlic preparations, such as garlic oil and aged garlic, contain less allicin and have reduced physiological activity.

• Scientific Classification:

Figure 2: Garlic bulb

Kingdom: Plantae

Clade: Angiosperms

Clade: Monocots

Order: Asparagales

Family: Amaryllidaceae

Genus: *Allium*

Species: *Allium sativum*

- **Common name:** Garlic
- **Family:** Amaryllidaceae
- **Biological source:** Garlic plant species from Amaryllidaceae family
- **Uses:** Antifungal, Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Antiviral, Antimicrobial, Cardioprotective, Antihypertensive, Hypocholesterolemic, Antidiabetic, Anticancer

- **Mechanism of action:**

Its action involves breaking the lipid bilayer of fungal cell membranes, resulting in cell death. Garlic has potent anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties in addition to its antifungal properties. These properties can help lessen oxidative stress, swelling, and redness in the infected nail bed, hastening the healing process. Garlic also stimulates local circulation, which improves defense and nutrient supply at the infection site. In addition to enhancing nail resilience and structure, the sulfur-rich components promote keratin synthesis, which promotes the growth of new, healthy nail tissue and inhibits infection recurrence. [15,16]

➤ ***Melaleuca alternifolia***

Tea tree oil, derived from the leaves of *Melaleuca alternifolia*, is widely recognized for its potent antifungal, antibacterial, and antiseptic properties. It has been extensively studied for its effectiveness in treating fungal infections, particularly onychomycosis (nail fungus). Its ability to penetrate deeply into the nail plate, allowing it to reach the site of infection and maintain a sustained antifungal effect.

- **Geographical location:**

In the Australian states of New South Wales and Queensland, the leaves and terminal branches of *Melaleuca alternifolia* (Myrtales: Myrtaceae) are steam-distilled to produce tea tree oil (TTO), an essential oil.

- **Chemical constituent:**

Monoterpenes and related alcohols such as Terpinen-4-ol, γ -Terpinene, α -Terpinene, and 1,8-Cineole (Eucalyptol) make up the majority of the almost 100 constituents in tea tree oil. Its terpinen-4-ol content is at least 30%, while its 1,8-cineole level is at most 15%. One of the main components of TTO, terpinen-4-ol, has potent antibacterial and anti-inflammatory qualities.

- **Scientific Classification:**

Figure 3: Tea tree leaf

Kingdom: Plantae

Clade: Angiosperms

Clade: Eudicots

Order: Myrtales

Family: Myrtaceae

Genus: *Melaleuca*

Species: *Melaleuca alternifolia*

- **Common name:** Tea tree

- **Family:** Myrtaceae

- **Biological source:** Tea tree oil is derived from the leaves of *Melaleuca alternifolia*, a small tree native to Australia

- **Uses:** Anti-fungal, anti-microbial, acne treatment, skin care, hair care, wound healing

- **Mechanism of action:**

Components like terpinen-4-ol play a central role in disrupting fungal cell membranes, leading to the inhibition of fungal growth. Beyond its antimicrobial benefits, tea tree oil exhibits soothing and anti-inflammatory effects that help calm irritated skin around infected nails, reducing redness and discomfort. Its natural healing properties also support tissue repair and regeneration, making it an ideal ingredient for nail care formulations aimed at restoring nail health, strengthening the cuticle, and preventing reinfection. Regular topical use can not only treat existing infections but also serve as a preventative measure for those prone to recurrent fungal issues. [17,18]

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials:

Ethyl cellulose, ethyl acetate, salicylic acid, methanol, camphor, castor oil, thioglycolic acid, and rose oil were obtained from Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., India. Garlic bulbs and tea tree oil were procured from the market. All the solvents were of analytical grade.

Method:

Extraction of Allicin from Garlic Bulb:

Figure 4: Soxhlet Apparatus

Fresh garlic cloves were selected, peeled, and ground into a fine paste to facilitate the release of active

constituents. The prepared paste was carefully loaded into the thimble of a Soxhlet apparatus, which was assembled with a condenser and round-bottom flask containing methanol as the extraction solvent. During the process, the methanol was heated to generate vapors, which condensed and repeatedly passed through the garlic sample, thereby enhancing the extraction of bioactive compounds. Continuous siphoning allowed repeated solvent circulation, ensuring efficient percolation through the sample. To achieve optimal recovery, three to four complete extraction cycles were performed. After sufficient cycling, the solvent was evaporated on a water bath to remove excess methanol, and the final concentrated garlic extract was obtained for further formulation studies. [19]

Identification test for phytoconstituent:

The extract was identified for phytoconstituent test such as steroids, flavonoids, alkaloids, carbohydrates, tannins, glycosides, terpenoids, terpene hydrocarbons, and phenols.

The presence of alkaloids can be confirmed using Mayer's or Dragendorff's test, where the addition of these reagents to the extract results in a creamy white (Mayer's) or orange-red (Dragendorff's) precipitate. Carbohydrates are identified using the Molisch's test, in which the appearance of a violet ring at the junction of sulfuric acid and the plant extract containing Molisch's reagent indicates their presence. Tannins are detected by the Ferric chloride test, where a blue-black or greenish-black coloration signifies tannin content. Lastly, steroids can be confirmed with the Salkowski's test, where a reddish-brown ring appears at the interface after adding chloroform and concentrated sulfuric acid. Glycosides were identified through the Keller-Killiani test, where the formation of a reddish-brown ring and bluish-green upper layer after treatment with glacial acetic acid, ferric chloride, and concentrated sulfuric acid indicates their presence. Terpenoids are detected using the Salkowski's test, where the appearance of a reddish or pink color upon treatment with sulfuric acid confirms their presence. For terpene hydrocarbons, the vanillin-sulfuric acid test is employed, where a pink to red coloration suggests their existence. Lastly, phenols are confirmed by the Ferric chloride test, where the

formation of a deep blue, green, or purple color indicates phenolic compounds. [20]

TLC method development:

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) is a technique used to separate chemical mixtures, discovered by M. Tswettin 1906. It is performed on a glass, plastic, or aluminium sheet coated with a thin layer of adsorbent material such as silica gel, aluminium oxide, or cellulose, which serves as the stationary phase. A sample is applied to the plate, and a solvent or solvent mixture (mobile phase) ascends the plate via capillary

action, separating compounds based on their interaction with the stationary phase. TLC is commonly used to monitor reaction progress, identify compounds, and determine purity. Separation is influenced by the polarity of compounds: polar compounds interact more strongly with the polar stationary phase (e.g., silica), moving more slowly, while less polar compounds travel farther, resulting in higher R_f values. Increasing the polarity of the mobile phase, such as by adding ethyl acetate to heptane, raises the R_f values of all compounds, though it typically doesn't reverse their order. [21]

Table 1: TLC Profile of tea tree oil

Stationary Phase	Silica gel TLC plates.
Mobile Phase (Solvent System)	Typically, a mixture of solvents like toluene, ethyl acetate, and formic acid (5:4:1) is used to separate the volatile compounds.
Detection	The TLC plate was examined in the iodine chamber.

Preparation of nail lacquer:

The medicated nail lacquer was formulated using a simple mixing method, as shown in Table 2. Initially, ethyl cellulose, the film-forming polymer, was dissolved in ethyl acetate under continuous stirring until a uniform solution was obtained. Once fully dissolved, camphor was added as a plasticizer to enhance the flexibility of the film. Ethanol, acting as a co-solvent, was then incorporated to aid in the dissolution and uniform dispersion of other components. Castor oil, serving both as a viscosity enhancer and additional plasticizer, was added to improve the consistency and spreadability of the formulation.

Subsequently, salicylic acid, serving as a keratolytic agent, and thioglycolic acid, acting as a permeation enhancer, were added in appropriate quantities and mixed thoroughly using a magnetic stirrer to ensure uniform dispersion. Following this, garlic extract and tea tree oil were incorporated into the formulation due to their well-documented antifungal properties. Garlic extract contains allicin, a bioactive compound known for its ability to inhibit fungal growth, while tea tree oil is rich in terpinen-4-ol, which exerts potent antifungal effects by disrupting fungal cell membranes. Finally, rose oil was added to enhance the sensory appeal of the formulation by providing a

pleasant fragrance. The final formulation was then filled into narrow-mouth containers and sealed tightly with appropriate liners and caps. The prepared nail lacquer was further optimized to achieve the desired therapeutic and physicochemical properties.

Formulation and development:

Screening of Excipients Based on Literature Research: As per the literature research on nail lacquer drug delivery systems in onychomycosis, most researchers have used the following excipients as mandatory for the preparation of nail lacquer formulation.

- **Film-forming Polymers:** The film-forming polymers are used in 10-20% concentrations. Around 15% apply to most of the research work
- **Solvents:** The solvents are used in 60 to 80% concentrations. Around 70-75% concentration applies to most of the research work.
- **Plasticizers:** The plasticizers are used in 1-5% concentrations. Around 5% applies to most of the research work.
- **Penetration Enhancers:** The penetration enhancers are used in 1-5% concentrations. Around 5% applies to most of the research work.

Table: 2 List of excipients used in nail lacquer formulation.

Chemicals	Uses
API	
Garlic	Exhibits antifungal and antimicrobial activity; used to treat nail infections.
Tea tree oil	Possesses strong antifungal and antibacterial properties; aids in nail infection treatment.
Polymer	
Ethyl cellulose (EC)	Film-forming polymer providing durable coating; controls drug release from lacquer.
Solvents	
Ethyl acetate	Primary solvent for dissolving polymer and drug; provides quick-drying property.
Ethanol	Acts as a co-solvent and antiseptic; assists in quick drying of lacquer.
Plasticizers	
Castor oil	Improves film flexibility and prevents cracking of the lacquer.
Camphor	Functions as a plasticizer and imparts a glossy finish to the coating.
Keratolytic agent	
Salicylic acid	Softens and removes thickened nail keratin layers; promotes drug penetration.
Permeation enhancer	
Thioglycolic acid	Disrupts disulfide bonds in nail keratin to enhance drug permeation.

Preliminary trials:

Preliminary trials were conducted to develop a nail lacquer formulation incorporating antifungal herbal extracts—garlic extract and tea tree oil—with the objective of evaluating the effect of varying concentrations of key excipients on the overall performance of the formulation. Four batches (F1–F4) were prepared by altering the composition of ingredients such as ethyl cellulose (film-forming agent), ethyl acetate (solvent), castor oil (plasticizer), camphor (penetration enhancer), thioglycolic acid (nail permeation enhancer), salicylic acid (keratolytic

agent), and ethanol (co-solvent). The independent variables in this study included the concentrations of film-former, plasticizer, solvent, and permeation enhancers. The dependent variables were the physicochemical properties of the lacquer such as drying time, film formation, adhesion and spreadability. These preliminary batches were developed to optimize the formulation for enhanced penetration through the nail plate, prolonged retention time, and uniform spreadability, while also ensuring acceptable cosmetic properties and ease of application.

Table 3: Trial batches for the formulation:

Name of Ingredient	F1	F2	F3	F4
Ethyl cellulose	15%	20%	25%	30%
Ethyl acetate	60%	60%	60%	60%
Salicylic acid	-	1%	-	2%
Ethanol	-	1%	2%	5%
Camphor	1%	-	2%	2%
Castor oil	2%	1%	1%	2%
Thioglycolic acid	5%	5%	10%	10%
Rose oil	1%	1%	1%	1%
Garlic extract	1%	1%	1%	1%
Tea tree oil	1%	1%	1%	1%

Physicochemical characterization:

A) Physical Appearance: The nail lacquer formulation was evaluated for physical appearances such as clarity, transparency, and any color changes in the formulations.

B) Drying Time: In this study, a brush applicator was used to apply the herbal nail lacquer mixture evenly across a petri plate. The stopwatch was used to record how long it took for the entire film to dry after the petri dish was left at room temperature. The formulation is deemed to be considerably dry when it does not stick to the finger after contact.^[22,23]

C) Non-volatile content. An evenly distributed 1 ± 0.2 g sample was placed on a Petri plate and kept at $105 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 hour. The sample was then allowed to cool before being weighed once more, and the weight difference was used to compute the non-volatile content [BIS, IS 9445:1994].

D) Blush test: On a glass plate, NL was poured until a consistent layer appeared. After that, it was dried for 24 hours under standard conditions. After that, the plate was submerged in a beaker filled with water for four hours, dipping half of the film in it. It was then taken off, left to dry for four hours, and the blush was examined.

E) Water Resistance: After taking the glass petri dish, the 2×2 cm² region was uniformly demarcated. On this designated section of the glass petri dish, 0.2 g of the herbal nail lacquer mixture was applied as a film, and it was allowed to dry at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The glass petri dish weight was then recorded and left in the beaker with the demineralized water for a full day. The plate is maintained so that the beaker is adequately submerged in the dry lacquer coating. The glass plate was taken out of the beaker solution after a day and cleaned with tissue paper. The weight differential was computed when the glass plate's weight was recorded once more. By utilizing a formula for the percentage weight gain of the film compared to its real weight after immersion in water, the water resistance of the nail lacquer formulation was ascertained.

F) In-vitro Adhesion: The glass petri dish was taken, and the 3.6×2.4 cm² area was uniformly marked. On

this designated section of the plate, a brush was used to apply about 0.25 g of herbal nail lacquer formulation, which was then dried for 24 hours at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. A scalpel with a 0.37 mm blade thickness was then used to cut the film into 1 mm sections that were both parallel and perpendicular in size. The film was then covered with cellophane tape, which was then pressed with a finger to smooth the film, leaving an unadhered piece of tape. A few minutes later, the nail lacquer film was pulled in manual form by removing the unadhered tape-free end. The square count method was used to determine how many film squares adhered to the tape overall, and the peel-off percentage is calculated using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ peel-off} = \frac{\text{Initial squares of the film} - \text{Final squares of film} \times 100}{\text{Initial squares of the film}}$$

G) Stability Study Analysis: The optimized formulation was kept for a month at intervals of 15 days at $30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $70 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity (RH). The non-volatile content, viscosity, drying time, film adhesion, water resistance, and in vitro drug release of the sample were all assessed.^[23]

Result and discussion:

The nail lacquer formulations containing garlic extract and tea tree oil were successfully prepared and evaluated. The selected herbal extracts, known for their antifungal potential, were incorporated without compromising the cosmetic elegance and spreadability of the lacquer. Preliminary observations indicated good film formation, uniform application, and satisfactory drying time.

Solvent selection is essential in nail lacquer formulation, as it ensures proper dissolution of ingredients, suitable viscosity, and smooth application. It aids in quick drying, uniform film formation, and effective spread of active components. The right solvent balance enhances stability, adhesion, and overall cosmetic appeal of the product.

Ethanol and ethyl acetate were selected as solvents in the formulation of the nail lacquer. Ethanol functions primarily as a diluent, aiding in the dissolution of active herbal extracts and film-forming polymers such as ethyl cellulose. It also contributes to adjusting the viscosity and improving the spreadability of the

formulation. Ethyl acetate, a fast-evaporating solvent, plays a key role in providing a smooth and even application on the nail surface. It significantly contributes to the quick drying of the lacquer and supports effective film formation and adhesion to the nail plate. A combination of ethanol and ethyl acetate was used to balance the lacquer's solubility, drying time, spreadability, and cosmetic appeal, ensuring optimal performance and user acceptability.

Identification test of phytoconstituents:

Allium sativum tested positive for alkaloids, carbohydrates, tannins, and steroids and *Melaleuca alternifolia* exhibited the presence of glycosides, terpenoids, terpene hydrocarbons, and phenols, indicating the presence of the main constituent i.e. Allicin and terpinen-4-ol.

Table 4: Phytochemical tests of *Allium sativum* & *Melaleuca alternifolia*

Tests	<i>Allium sativum</i>	<i>Melaleuca alternifolia</i>
Alkaloid	+	-
Glycosides	-	+
Carbohydrates	+	-
Reducing sugars	-	-
Tannins	+	-
Steroids	+	-
Proteins & AA	-	-
Terpenoids	-	+
Terpene hydrocarbons	-	+
Phenols	-	+

TLC method development:

Among the various mobile phases evaluated for the Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) analysis of tea tree oil, the mobile phase consisting of toluene: ethyl acetate: formic acid (5:4:1) provided the most satisfactory resolution. This combination resulted in a well-defined spot with an appropriate R_f value of 0.65

indicating effective separation of the major active constituent i.e. α - Terpine-4-ol. The clarity, compactness, and reproducibility of the spot confirmed the suitability of this mobile phase for qualitative analysis of tea tree oil.

Detection: TLC plate examined in the iodine chamber.

Figure 5: TLC Profile of tea tree oil

Physicochemical evaluation:

A.) Physical Appearance: Among all batches, Formulation F3 and F4 showed superior clarity and transparency, which can be attributed to the

optimized combination of ethanol and ethyl acetate, which effectively balanced the lacquer's solubility and contributed to the uniform distribution of film-forming agents and plasticizers, resulting in an elegant finish. The formulated nail lacquer was observed to be transparent and non-gritty, with a smooth and aesthetically pleasing appearance.

B.) Drying Time: The drying time of nail lacquer is an important consideration when evaluating its efficacy. The drying time for the entire batch ended up being between 30 and 80 seconds. However, the drying time decreases as the concentration of the polymer increases. Compared to the less viscous solution, the more viscous solution takes longer for the solvent to evaporate. The drying time for formulas F3 and F4 was therefore noticeably longer than that of the other batches.

C.) Non-volatile content: The solid film that remains on the nail surface following full solvent evaporation is represented by this non-volatile residue, which essentially forms a continuous covering across the nail plate. As the concentration of polymers increases, the non-volatile portion of the nail lacquer also increases. In the formulation, the amount of polymer has a direct impact on the non-volatile content. Hence, the non-volatile fraction rises in tandem with the polymer concentration, as demonstrated by Batch F4, whose non-volatile content was found to be $27.2 \pm 2.10\%$.^[24]

D.) Blush test: The Blush test was used to examine how the physical characteristics of the lacquer were affected by the external climate and water exposure. It was found that the film's brightness remained unaffected, which may be because the nail lacquer contains a hydrophobic polymer.

H.) antifungal potential.^[24]

Additionally, there was no evidence of blistering or full peeling off.

E.) Water Resistance: The water resistance test has a direct relationship with the polymer concentration. The water resistance of the formulated nail lacquer increases with increasing polymer concentration. Of all the formulations tested, the F4 batch showed the lowest water loss percentage ($1.05 \pm 0.10\%$), suggesting superior water resistance in comparison to other formulated nail lacquer batches.

F.) In-vitro Adhesion: Among all the formulations, F4 exhibited the highest in-vitro adhesion ($7.87 \pm 2.48\%$), reflecting its superior binding ability and uniform film formation on the nail plate. This performance can be linked to its optimized composition, particularly the higher concentration of ethyl cellulose (30%), which provides a thicker and stronger film. The presence of salicylic acid (2%) along with thioglycolic acid (10%) enhances surface roughness of the nail, promoting better interlocking and adhesion. Additionally, ethanol supports uniform spreading of the lacquer, while camphor and castor oil act as plasticizers that maintain flexibility and prevent cracking, collectively resulting in improved adhesive strength.

G.) Stability Study Analysis: The developed nail lacquer was evaluated for stability over a 1 month period. Parameters such as physical appearance, drying time, gloss, non-volatile content, blush test, water resistance, and in-vitro adhesion showed no significant changes during storage. This consistency demonstrates that the formulation is stable and successfully maintains its essential physicochemical properties. Therefore, the nail lacquer can be regarded as a reliable and effective formulation with promising

Table 5: Evaluation Parameters of formulated batches

Evaluation Parameters:	Physical Appearance	Drying time (s)	Gloss	Non-volatile content (%)	Blush test	Water Resistance (%)	In-vitro Adhesion (%)
F1	Translucent	30 ± 2	+	23.1 ± 0.32	Pass	2.50 ± 0.23	5.59 ± 1.25

F2	Translucent	50 ± 3	+	24.8 ± 0.56	Pass	2.02 ± 0.20	6.54 ± 1.14
F3	Clear, transparent	60 ± 5	++	25.6 ± 1.88	Pass	1.25 ± 0.15	7.36 ± 2.54
F4	Clear, transparent	80 ± 2	++++	27.2 ± 2.10	Pass	1.05 ± 0.10	7.87 ± 2.48

Figure 6: Gloss test

Figure 7: Water resistance

Figure 8: Smoothness of film

Figure 9: Final appearance of Nail Lacquer

CONCLUSION

The antifungal nail lacquer was successfully formulated using natural antifungal agents (garlic extract and tea tree oil) in combination with ethyl cellulose as a film-former. This approach overcomes several drawbacks of conventional dosage forms such as creams, ointments, and oral antifungal therapies, including skin irritation, gastrointestinal side effects, allergic reactions, and nail discoloration. The formulated lacquer provides a uniform film on the nail surface, ensuring prolonged contact time, better penetration, and enhanced therapeutic efficacy against fungal infections. Among the tested ratios, the batch containing 30% ethyl cellulose, 5% ethanol, and a proportionally higher amount of ethyl acetate showed the best results, making it the most suitable solvent system for nail lacquer formulation. Among the tested formulations, F4 was identified as the

optimized batch as it exhibited the highest in-vitro adhesion ($7.87 \pm 2.48\%$), stronger film-forming capacity, and better binding to the nail plate. This superior performance can be attributed to its higher concentration of ethyl cellulose (30%) providing a robust film, synergistic keratolytic action of salicylic acid (2%) and thioglycolic acid (10%) enhancing nail surface roughness for better adhesion, and balanced use of ethanol, camphor, and castor oil to promote uniform spreading and flexibility of the film. Therefore, the F4 formulation can be considered the most suitable and optimized antifungal nail lacquer, offering a promising alternative to conventional antifungal dosage forms for effective management of onychomycosis.

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